

ABSTRACTS

CIK- 12th International Conference in collaboration with ESCA and SINGEP

Oct. 23-25, 2024, Hybrid

Theme: Climate Change, Entrepreneurship, Innovation, and Sustainable Development

CYRUS Institute of Knowledge

Cambridge, USA,

ESCA Ecole de Management, Casablanca Morocco,

And

**Simpósio Internacional de Gestão de Projetos,
Inovação e Sustentabilidade (SINGEP)**

October 23-25, 2024

Hybrid

CIK Conference Accepted Abstracts

Co-sponsors:

- **Bentley University – USA**
- ***ESCA, Casablanca - Morocco***
- **UNINOVE University (São Paulo) – Brazil**

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Conference Theme:

**CLIMATE CHANGE, ENTREPRENEURSHIP, INNOVATION,
AND SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT**

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BRAIN DRAIN: PROPOSAL FOR A MANAGEMENT MODEL OF THE CAPES FULL DOCTORAL PROGRAM IN THE LIGHT OF THE RESOURCE-BASED VIEW

Sara Cristina Alves dos Santos and Emerson Antonio Maccari

Oninove, Brazil

Abstract

Globalization and the network society, with processes that go beyond national borders, mark the beginning of the 21st century. These factors challenge Higher Education Institutions to internationalize to train high-level human resources, highlighting the need of the State in prioritizing and encouraging academic mobility. In Brazil, the Coordination for the Improvement of Higher Education Personnel (CAPES) is the main agency for promoting

internationalization, allowing scholarship holders to complete their stricto sensu postgraduate studies in full abroad through the Full Doctorate Program. However, this can lead to brain drain when researchers do not return to their country of origin, causing losses. This dissertation investigates strategies for managing the CAPES Full Doctorate Program in light of the Resource-Based View (RBV), considering brain drain. The objective of the study is to propose a Program management model in accordance with the RBV theory, which considers Human Resources as sources of sustainable competitive advantage. The research is qualitative in nature, exploratory in approach and based on a single case study. Data collection included documentary survey on the Ministry of Education - MEC/CAPES portal, data from the Sucupira Platform (GeoCAPES), semi-structured interviews with managers from the Directorate of International Relations (DRI) CAPES, students and graduates of the Program, and semi-structured questionnaires with students, allowing data triangulation according to Yin (2001). The analysis followed the Content Analysis technique proposed by Bardin (2011). The main results indicate that, despite the return commitment established with CAPES in the Grant and Scholarship Acceptance Term, some participating researchers do not return to Brazil due to lack of resources, infrastructure, political instability, better salaries or

scholarships abroad, participation in research groups at renowned universities and negotiations with CAPES (Novação). Data analysis led to the Proposal of a Management Model that replaces the interstice with the researcher's contribution through an Alternative Academic Activities Plan, with an impact and relevance equivalent to the investment made. For the effectiveness of the proposed Model, it is suggested for future studies to calibrate Academic Activities with ad hoc consultants. This work contributes to the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs 4, 8, 16 and 17), demonstrating its social impact.

Keywords: Internationalization of postgraduate studies, Brain drain, Full Doctorate, CAPES,